

National languages:

Technical Reports

Software for mobilisation and efficient use of resources in timber transportation

Videos

Creating your own estate plan via the online portal (MojGozdar)

A system for quality assessment of forestry contractors (eGOZD)

Prefabricated modular construction system made from Normandy hardwoods

Standardization of available forest data: support wood mobilization in Friuli Venezia Giulia

Articles

Manufacturing steps sheet of LVL (micro-laminated wood) of beech

Forest inventory in a pocket: The Di-Gozd Digital Forest Inventory App

MojGozdar: A Digital Tool for Quality Classification and Marketing of Roundwood

MojGozdar portal: Due Diligence and Traceability System for forest wood trade

UAV Technology Revolutionizing Forest Management in the Eastern Alps

Growing Stock Volume Map to support forest operation planning

Forest Adaptation to Climate Change

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Technical Reports

Drones and multispectral cameras in forest health monitoring (FHM)

Videos

The "sustainable bee forest" concept and implementation

Chestnut forests management for quality products and promote carbon sequestration

GeoSuber Platform to manage oak forest

Articles

Drones and multispectral cameras in forest health monitoring (FHM)

BioClimSol: a decision support system integrating future climate and ground conditions

« Foresters it's your turn to play » An educational game to teach primary school children about climate change in forests

GO SURF: A Course on GIS and Remote Sensing Data for Monitoring Forest Ecosystems

Application of the SlideforMap model for the hydrological risk assessment in sustainably managed forests

Foster Forest: A Game to Imagine the Forest of the Future

Drones and multispectral cameras in forest health monitoring (FHM)

Sustainable forest management and ecosystem services

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Technical Reports

Quantification of Carbon Stock in Sustainable Forest Management Plan

The Index of Biodiversity Potential tool: How to implement it in forest management?

OG SPNA: Precision silviculture in Nouvelle-Aquitaine Vigill'entre

Videos

Community forest arrangements as ideal instance for the realization of the profit-sharing model of PRIFORMAN Project

Articles

Estimation of Soil Carbon Credits: Innovative Approach of CO₂MARCHE

Developing a Novel Martelloscope for Assessing Biodiversity & Stock Volume

Biomass accounting for Sustainable Forest Management Plans

Technology at the service of forest renewal - mapping with drone and GPS in plantation projects to stake out the stand

A User-Friendly Platform for Bridging the Gap between Carbon Credit Demand and Supply

Sustainable forest management and ecosystem services

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Group Certification for Sustainable Forest Management: Promoting Shared Forest Management and Ecosystem Services Enhancement

The ARCHI method: a tool for diagnosing tree vitality

Quantification of carbon stock in sustainable forest management plan

Decisional support system for enhancing forest management efficiency

Empowering Sustainable Forest Management in the European Context: The PRI.FOR.MAN Decision Support System

Non-Wood Forest Products

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Geolocation and monitoring of animals to identify possible incidents and improve the management of animals and pastures

Mobile charcoal pile prototype for biochar production in situ

Resin Data Observatory

Endothermic treatments with Trichoderma spp. in chestnut groves

Articles

Innovation and Technology Transfer in the Treatment of Chestnut Blight

Business development for honey from the bee forest

Diversifying edible wild mushroom cultivation with new native species in Catalonia, Spain

OG SAMBUCOSVALOR: A road to elderberry valorisation

Pine Resin: Untapped Potential for Sustainable Industrial Innovation

Value the traditional chestnuts production

National languages:

Technical Reports

Review assesses the state of the art regarding the use of livestock for ecosystem management in Mediterranean landscapes

NEWTON - NEtWork Operational Group for agroforestry in Tuscany: criteria and indicators for the certification of the sustainable management of an agroforestry system PEFC

Videos

Development of an autonomous and digitalized feeding system for pigs

Use of Keyline for planting cork oaks and holm oaks in agro-forestry systems

Articles

Northern climate and apple varieties as a source for innovation

Agroforestry in the Netherlands - Integrating trees on farms. How to get started with agroforestry in the province of North Holland?

Are short rotation coppice a solution in future regional biorefineries?

GO BUCHDENS - New local hedges development sector: densified logs

REPORT ON OPERATIONAL GROUP "NEWTON" - Agroforestry Network in Tuscany: a regional Operational Group to spread agroforestry knowledge and innovations

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"Agroforestry in Austria" network

Practitioner-oriented consulting on agroforestry systems in Austria

